

Effect of Sub-lethal Doses of Zinc Chloride on Antioxidant Enzyme Activity of *Cirrhina mrigala*

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ABSTRACT

Three groups of *Cirrhina mrigala* (one year old) were exposed, separately, to sub-lethal concentrations (96-hr LC₅₀, 2/3rd of LC₅₀, 1/4th of LC₅₀ and 1/5th of LC₅₀) of ZnCl₂ in glass aquaria along with the control group. After 30 days exposure, the fish were sacrificed and peroxidase activity in liver and kidney were determined. The peroxidase activity in both organs of ZnCl₂ exposed fish were compared with control. The physico-chemical parameters of the experimental media viz. pH, dissolved oxygen, carbon dioxide, total hardness, calcium, magnesium and total ammonia were also monitored twice a day. The results showed that the peroxidase activity was significantly increased in both the organs as a result of ZnCl₂ exposure in all the treatments than control. The peroxidase activities in all treated and control fish groups were found lower in kidney than in the liver.

Keyword: *Cirrhina mrigala*, Zinc, Sub-lethal, Peroxidase activity, Organs

INTRODUCTION

The natural aquatic environments are being polluted by the disposal of untreated effluents released from sewage, agricultural and industrial sources. Among aquatic pollutants, there existed organic and inorganic compounds such as combustible substances, petroleum products, phenols, textile dyes and heavy metals. Metals are important ecological pollutants that may cause mutagenic and cytotoxic effects in the aquatic organisms [1]. Fish are more vulnerable to the harmful impacts of pollutants as they can uptake heavy metals from the surrounding environment and accumulate them in various organs and tissues resulting into biomagnification in the food chain making the fish an important indicator of metallic ions pollution [2].

Essential heavy metals like zinc, chromium, copper, nickel, molybdenum, iron and cobalt play an important role in several biological processes. However, the essential metals, when found at higher concentrations, can cause toxic effects on the organisms [3]. Zinc is widely used in solar panels, paints, semiconductors and waste water treatment plants [4]. It is an essential trace element and a structural component of many enzymes. For metabolism and normal development, small quantities of zinc are required upto permissible limits. But when the concentration of zinc exceeds beyond the physiological requirement of the fish body, it becomes toxic [5]. At higher concentrations, ZnCl₂ can induce oxidative damage and antioxidant disturbances in the tissues of fish which ultimately lead towards inhibition of glutathione reductase along with an increase in antioxidant defense, as an adaptive response [6].

The organisms have developed antioxidant defense system to protect their cells against oxidative damage caused by heavy metals [7]. Oxidative stress is an imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and antioxidant defense system of the cell. Highly reactive ions, molecules or compounds are formed by incomplete reduction of one electron of oxygen that induces alterations in the physiological responses of the living organism. As a consequence of metallic ions exposure, formation of reactive oxygen species is enhanced that may cause peroxidation of lipids, proteins, DNA and even apoptotic cell

death [8]. Elevated levels of heavy metals, like zinc, in the tissues of fish can produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as hydrogen peroxide, superoxide and hydroxyl radicals [9]. Among the antioxidant enzymes, peroxidase protects the tissues from damage caused by harmful effects of H₂O₂ as well as lipid peroxidation [10]. The liver plays an important role in regulating the metabolism of the body, involving detoxification of xenobiotics and is the first target of ingested oxidants. It serves as an important tissue in studying the role of GSH-Px in the protection from lipid peroxidation [11]. In addition to this, fish kidney is pivotal organ, involved in osmoregulation, detoxification and excretion of xenobiotics [12].

Metallic ions released from various industries are discharged untreated in the riverine systems of Pakistan causing adverse effects on the indigenous fish fauna, especially major carps and their populations that are continuously declining in the natural aquatic habitats [13]. In the field of ecotoxicology, the use of oxidative stress biomarkers is gaining importance because they provide an early warning to the potentially hazardous substances in the aquatic environments. Therefore, the present study was conducted to determine the effect of sub-lethal doses of ZnCl₂ on antioxidant enzyme activity in the liver and kidney of *Cirrhina mrigala* under controlled laboratory conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proposed research work was conducted in the laboratories of Fisheries Research Farms, Department of Zoology, Wildlife and Fisheries, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad. One year old *Cirrhina mrigala* were procured from the ponds and brought to the laboratory for two weeks acclimatization in cemented tanks. Fish were fed with pelleted feed (30 % DP and 3.00 Kcalg⁻¹ DE) twice daily. After acclimation period, healthy fish of similar weights and lengths, were selected for these experiments. Pure chloride compound of zinc (ZnCl₂) was dissolved in 1000 mL deionized water for the preparation of metal stock solution. Three fish groups (n = 10) were transferred to the glass aquaria of 50-L water capacity to check the effect of ZnCl₂ on peroxidase activity in the selected tissues viz. liver and kidney of *Cirrhina mrigala*. Fish

were exposed to 96-hr LC₅₀ of zinc chloride (56.67±3.41 mgL⁻¹) as determined by [14] and 2/3rd, 1/4th and 1/5th of 96-hr LC₅₀ values, separately, for 30 days in glass aquaria. Each test was conducted with three replications for each test dose along with a control group (un-stressed). Water pH and dissolved oxygen were monitored on 12-hr basis by using digital meters viz. HANNA HI-8424 and HI-9146 while carbon dioxide, total hardness, calcium, magnesium and total ammonia contents of water were determined by following the methods of [15]. After 30 days exposure period, fish were sacrificed and their tissues viz. liver and kidney were isolated for the enzyme assay.

Peroxidase Assay

Red blood cells were removed from the liver and kidney by rinsing these organs with phosphate buffer of pH 6.5 (0.2 M) and homogenized in cold buffer (1:4 W/V) using a blender. After homogenization, both the organ's homogenate was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 10,000 rpm at 4 °C, separately. After centrifugation process, clear supernatant was preserved at -4 °C for enzyme assay while residue was discarded. For the determination of peroxidase activity, the sample was subjected to enzyme assay [16]. Activity of peroxidase was assessed by measuring the conversion of guaiacol to tetraguaiacol, spectrophotometrically, at a wavelength of 470 nm. The required reagents for enzyme assay were 0.2 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.5), guaiacol and hydrogen peroxide. Guaiacol (750 µL) was added to phosphate buffer (47 mL) and mixed well on vortex agitator. After agitation H₂O₂ (0.3 mL) was added to buffer solution. The reaction mixture contained buffered substrate solution (3 mL) and enzyme extract (0.06 mL).

A cuvette containing 3 mL of blank (phosphate buffer) solution was inserted into the spectrophotometer and set it to zero. Then a cuvette containing buffered substrate solution was placed in the spectrophotometer and initiation of reaction was occurred by adding enzyme extract. The reaction time was 3 minutes and the absorbance was observed after the specified time.

The peroxidase activity was calculated by using following formula:

$$\text{Activity (Unit / mL)} = \frac{\Delta A / 3}{26.60 \times 60 / 3000}$$

Table 1: Peroxidase activity (UmL⁻¹) in the liver and kidney of *Cirrhina mrigala* after chronic exposure of ZnCl₂

Organs	96-hr LC ₅₀	2/3 rd of LC ₅₀	1/4 th of LC ₅₀	1/5 th of LC ₅₀	Control	Overall Means±SD
Liver	0.564±0.009 a	0.424±0.005 b	0.396±0.006 c	0.244±0.002 d	0.126±0.002 e	0.305±0.004 a
Kidney	0.146±0.002 a	0.088±0.002 b	0.062±0.002 c	0.043±0.001 d	0.021±0.003 e	0.072±0.002 b
Overall Means±SD	0.355±0.005 a	0.256±0.003 b	0.229±0.003 c	0.143±0.001 d	0.073±0.002 e	

Figure 1: Peroxidase Activity (UmL⁻¹) of Liver and Kidney of *Cirrhina mrigala* at Different Treatments of ZnCl₂

CONCLUSION

In the liver and kidney of *Cirrhina mrigala*, the activity of antioxidant enzyme “peroxidase” was found significantly increased after exposure to various concentrations of ZnCl₂. Among both the selected organs, statistically significant and higher peroxidase activity was observed in the fish liver as compared to kidney.

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REFERENCES

1. A.R. Karbassi, I. Bayati, F. Moattar, Origin and chemical partitioning of heavy metals in riverbed sediments, Int. J. Environ. Sci. Tech. 3 (2006) 35-42.
2. V.I. Lushchak, Environmentally induced oxidative stress in aquatic animals, Aquat. Toxicol. 101 (2011) 13-30.
3. P. Sivaperumal, T.V. Sankar, P.G. Viswanathan Nair, Heavy metal concentrations in fish, shellfish and fish products from internal markets of India vis-a-vis international standards, Food Chem. 102 (2007) 612-620.
4. Y.S. Zimmermann, A. Schaffer, C. Hugi, K. Fent, P.F. Corvini, M. Lenz, Organic photovoltaics: Potential fate and effects in the environment, Environ. Int. 49 (2012) 128-140.
5. V. Shukla, P. Rathi, K.V. Sastry, Effect of cadmium individually and in combination with other metals on the nutritive value of fresh water fish, *Channa punctatus*, J. Environ. Biol. 23 (2002) 105-110.
6. J.L. Franco, T. Posser, J.J. Mattos, A. Sanchez-Chardi, R. Trevisan, C.S. Oliveira, P.S. Carvalho, R.B. Leal, M.R. Marques, A.C. Bainy, Biochemical alterations in juvenile carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) exposed to zinc: Glutathione reductase as a target, Mar. Environ. Res. 66 (2008) 88-89.
7. S. George, M. Gubbins, A. MacIntosh, W. Reynolds, V. Sabine, A. Scott, J. Thain, A comparison of pollutant biomarker responses with transcriptional responses in European flounders (*Platichthys flesus*) subjected to estuarine pollution, Mar. Environ. Res. 58 (2004) 571-575.
8. D.R. Livingstone, Oxidative stress in aquatic organisms in relation to pollution and agriculture, Rev. Med. Vet. 154 (2003) 427-430.
9. L. Cao, W. Huang, J. Liu, X. Yin, S. Dou, Accumulation and oxidative stress biomarkers in Japanese flounder larvae and juveniles under chronic cadmium exposure, Comp. Biochem. Physiol. 151 (2010) 386-392.
10. X. Li, Y. Liu, L. Song, J. Liu, Responses of antioxidant systems in the hepatocytes of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.) to the toxicity of microcystin-LR, Toxicol. 42 (2003) 85-89.
11. J.K. Miller, E. Brzezinska-Slebodzinska, F.C. Madsen, Oxidative stress, antioxidants, and animal function, J. Dairy Sci. 76 (1993) 2812-2823.
12. D.A. Vesey, Transport pathways for cadmium in the intestine and kidney proximal tubule: Focus on the interaction with essential metals, Toxicol. Lett. 198 (2010) 13-19.
13. H. Azmat, M. Javed, Acute toxicity of chromium to *Catla catla*, *Labeo rohita* and *Cirrhina mrigala* under laboratory conditions, Int. J. Agric. Biol. 13 (2011) 961-965.
14. S. Abdullah, M. Javed, S. Yaqub, N. Ahmad, Metal bioaccumulation patterns in major carps during acute toxicity tests, Int. J. Agric. Biol. 13 (2011) 756-760.
15. A.P.H.A., Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater, 20th ed., American Public Health Association, New York, 1998, pp. 1193.
16. P.M. Civello, G.A. Martinez, A.R. Chaves, M.C. Anon, Peroxidase from strawberry fruit by partial purification and determination of some properties, J. Agr. Food Chem. 43 (1995) 2596-2601.
17. O.M. Awoyemi, K.A. Bawa-Allah, A.A. Otitolaju, Accumulation and anti-oxidant enzymes as biomarkers of heavy metal exposure in *Clarias gariepinus* and *Oreochromis niloticus*, Appl. Ecol. Environ. Sci. 2 (2014) 114-122.
18. E.O. Farombi, O.A. Adelowo, Y.R. Ajimoko, Biomarkers of oxidative stress and heavy metal levels as indicators of environmental pollution in African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) from Nigeria Ogun River, Int. J. Env. Res. Pub. He. 4 (2007) 158-165.
19. A. Alkaladi, M. Afifi, Y.Y. Mosleh, O. Abu-Zinada, Ultra structure alteration of sublethal concentrations of zinc oxide nanoparticles on Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and the protective effects of vitamins C and E, Life Sci. J. 11 (2014) 257-262.
20. O. Firat, H.Y. Cogun, S. Aslanyavrusu, F. Kargin, Antioxidant responses and metal accumulation in tissues of Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* under Zn, Cd and Zn + Cd exposures, J. Appl. Toxicol. 29 (2009) 295-301.

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